

The Mosasaur 12 (2002):7-29 (dvps.org)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8271535>

PROVENANCE OF SILICIFIED PALEOZOIC INVERTEBRATE FOSSILS DISPERSED IN NEOGENE - QUATERNARY AGE SEDIMENTS ACROSS THE NEW JERSEY ATLANTIC COASTAL PLAIN

William Kuehne¹, Frank Hajzer¹ and Les Spears²

¹Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, PO Box 686, Plymouth Meeting, PA, 19462, dvpsnews@gmail.com

²Avocational paleontologist, Mullica Hill, New Jersey

Abstract - The present investigation of the provenance of silicified invertebrate Paleozoic fossils on the New Jersey Atlantic Coastal Plain (ACP) adds 131 Paleozoic fossils recovered from eight new sites to the six sites previously reported. Fossils are dispersed in the surficial geology formations and Pleistocene alluvium across the ACP. Below taxonomic class, there was little correlation between Paleozoic taxa found on the ACP to Paleozoic formations in northern New Jersey. The ACP taxa are mixed, dominated by tabulate and rugose corals and poriferids but also include crinoids, brachiopods, bryozoans and a single trilobite. Aragonitic bivalves, gastropods and others are notably absent, brachiopods are expressed mostly as external molds on poriferids. Most specimens are worn and weathered, but a proportion are pristine and sharp-edged suggesting an ice-rafting event in addition to the Neogene fluvial event generally accepted as their means of transit.

INTRODUCTION

Explanatory notes

In the context of this report, “Exotic,” means foreign, out of place, applied to a clast from a non-contiguous, distant, earlier geochronological age formation and lodged in more recent, unrelated and unconsolidated sediments. “Parent,” means the geological formation from which an exotic clast was derived. “Host,” means the geological formation in which an exotic clast is embedded or resides on its surface. Identifications of taxa at species level in this report are mostly tentative, designated by the leading prefix, “cf.” The New Jersey Atlantic Coastal Plain will be referred by the acronym, “ACP.”

Paleozoic fossils on the ACP

Exotic Paleozoic fossils are occasionally associated with Neogene-Quaternary surficial geology formations and in overspreading alluvium on the ACP. It is problematical whether the fossils are actually in-situ in these formations or are alluvial, the latter being more likely. To the six Paleozoic fossil sites on the ACP previously reported, this investigation adds eight more for a total of 14, ranging from Monmouth County in the north to Cape May County in the south (Howell and Hale, 1946, Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2020). Those found on the ACP are at least 100 kilometers removed from their nearest possible parent Paleozoic formations of northern New Jersey. Taxa are mostly tabulate and rugose corals but include poriferids, stromatoporoids, stromatolites, brachiopods, crinoids, bryozoans and rarely trilobites. The fossils are silicified, either preserved free form or

more rarely embedded in a matrix of nodular chert formed in limestone and dolomite. These taxa also exist in Paleozoic shale but seldom preserve long enough to reach the ACP. The presence of such ancient fossils from distant parent rocks, many unworn and mixed with much more recent deposits, is enigmatic, and, in this report, we attempt to elucidate their provenance by identifying the fossils,

their host formations, locating their parent rocks, discovering their mode of transport and time of arrival on the ACP. From background research in geological and paleontological literature there is a paucity of information about exotic Paleozoic fossils on the ACP or elsewhere emphasizing the importance of this investigation as a contribution to fill the gap. A typical collecting site is included as **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. The Mullica Hill collecting site, a small tributary of Raccoon Creek. Note loose gravel float along the stream edges containing occasional exotic Paleozoic fossils. Such fossils are believed to originate in exposures upstream from this location.

Chert

As the fossils are either chert themselves or are embedded in a chert matrix, a study of their genesis may be useful background in interpreting their provenance. Chert is a form of microcrystalline quartz which forms diagenetically in both inorganic and biogenic limestone by processes not well understood (Morris, 2010). It occurs as isolated nodules or in layers (Chert, online), and, if the limestone is biogenic, the endogenous calcareous fossils may be replaced with silicified replicas. The silicified replicas often preserve the fine detail of the original taxon but take on the color of the host formation. Aragonitic bivalves and gastropods tend to dissolve away in the limestone before silicification takes place leaving only their molds and casts. Calcitic forms such as anthozoans and poriferids are preserved as their silicified replicas

(Silicification, online). Brachiopods do not preserve well and commonly only express themselves as external molds impressed on silicified forms often poriferids. As weathering and erosion disintegrate their host rock, the more resistant fossiliferous chert is disengaged into adjoining colluvial deposits eventually dispersed distally as alluvium. Chert occurs in black, gray, white, tan and red forms which help to identify parent rock; however, the chert often weathers to lighter colors thus concealing the parent.

Host formations

ACP surficial geology formations harboring Paleozoic fossils are listed in **Table 1** with their geochronological age. In the Holocene, Gallagher (1981) has reported fossiliferous chert nodules in gravel on Holocene New Jersey beaches. The Fossil Forum also has posted

reports of Paleozoic fossils found on New Jersey beaches (The Fossil Forum, online). Paleozoic fossils are reported on the beach at Cape May Point State Park (Sunset Beach), Higbee Beach and Reeds Point beach along in the Delaware River Estuary (US And Canadian Fossil Sites, online). Howell and Hale (1946) collected Paleozoic fossils from the “Pennsauken Gravel” at Princeton reporting that the specimens were collected from the surface and did not confirm in-situ state. The fossils were reported to be of a buff color attributed to the Onondaga Limestone of Sussex County although the National Geologic Map Database – Onondaga Formation reports only dark gray chert in the formation but, presumably, weathered to buff when recovered at the Princeton site (Onondaga Limestone, online). Howell and Hale (1946) report only three coralline taxa, listed in **Table 2** along with eight brachiopods. Their specimens were dedicated to the Princeton University Museum. Kuehne W. and Kuehne, A. (2020) reported collections from five sites across the ACP ranging from Monmouth to Cape May counties in alluvium associated with Upper Cretaceous, Paleogene and Quaternary deposits, 92 specimens, now residing in the New Jersey State

Museum. Newell et al. (2000) and Salisbury and Knapp (1917) report the presence of fossiliferous chert in the Bridgeton Formation on the ACP, implying, but not verifying, in-situ state. Newell et al. (2000) also report Paleozoic chert in alluvium derived from the Bridgeton Formation not confirming fossiliferous nature nor in-situ state. Fariakas et al. (1978) and Newell et al. 2000) both acknowledge that the Cohansey Formation contains Paleozoic chert nodules, potentially fossiliferous. If the chert is from a fossiliferous limestone, then it is likely fossiliferous. Summarizing, the Holocene and these three formations on the ACP, in order of age, Cohansey and Bridgeton, Miocene, and Pennsauken, Pliocene, are associated with fossiliferous Paleozoic chert as shown in **Table 2**. Also mantling the ACP are Qwcp, Weathered Coastal Plain Deposits, and Pleistocene alluvium making it problematic whether the surficial formations or the overspreading alluvium harbor the Paleozoic fossils. All confirmed specific Paleozoic fossil collection sites on the ACP, including those in this report, are plotted in **Figure 2** in relationship to surface geology formations (Fullerton et al., 2003).

Stratigraphy	Age	Paleozoic fossils	Chert	In-situ	Reference
Englishtown Formation	Upper Cretaceous	Yes	Yes	N/A	(Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2020)
Pensauken Formation	Pliocene	Yes	Yes	N/A	(Howell and Hale, 1946]
Bridgeton Formation	Miocene	Yes	Yes	Yes	(Newell et al., 2000), (Weller, 1903)
Beacon Hill Gravel	Miocene	Yes		Yes	(Stanford, 2020)
Cape May Formation	Pleistocene	Unknown			
Holocene	Recent	Yes		Yes	(Gallagher, 1981)
Cohansey Sand	Miocene	Yes	Yes	Yes	(Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2020)
Alluvium from the Bridgeton Formation	Quaternary	Yes			(Newell et al., 2000)

Table 1. Surface geology formations on the ACP associated with exotic Paleozoic fossils.

Outside of New Jersey, in Delaware, Pickett and Windish (1992) reported Paleozoic fossiliferous chert nodules from borrow pits along the Delaware Atlantic

Coastal Plain and attributed them to glacial outwash down the Delaware River Estuary. In South Carolina, Landmeyer et al. (2019) describe fossiliferous chert in

iron cemented strata and in surrounding unconsolidated sediments within the Quaternary Pinehurst Formation on the South Carolina Atlantic Coastal Plain. Morris (2010) reports exotic fossiliferous chert at several midwestern sites. A silicified favositid, was found on a gravel bar said to be Pleistocene drift, in Chatham, Ohio (Silicified fossil coral, online).

Parent rocks

Although potentially fossil-bearing Paleozoic biogenic limestone formations occur to the west in adjacent Pennsylvania and to the north in New York State, parsimony suggests that the Paleozoic fossils on the ACP derive from the closest sources which are north of the ACP in the Ridge and Valley and Green Pond Mountain Outlier Provinces of New Jersey **Figure 2**. This study focuses on Class Cnidaria, Subclass Anthozoa, which peaked in the Ordovician – Devonian Periods. Maps of the limestone and dolomite formations in this interval, extracted from New Jersey bedrock geology (Dalton et., 2014) are presented in

Table 2, limestone and **Table 3**, dolomite. Fossiliferous chert from these formations can outwash onto the ACP by either fluvial or glacial processes, possibly both, in singular or recurrent events. Salisbury and Knapp (1917) assert, “Much of the chert comes from the Beacon Hill Formation which once overspread the ACP but has since been reduced to a few scattered outcrops on higher elevations along the Atlantic coast,” The Beacon Hill Formation is now considered to be part of the Cohansey Formation of Miocene age (Newell et al., 2000). Weller (1903) commenting on the Bridgeton Formation, “Some of the bits of chert contain fossils which have been identified as Devonian” implying in-situ status. Then, for Paleozoic fossils, the most productive formations and their associated colluvium/alluvium are the Beacon Hill, secondarily, Cohansey and finally Bridgeton. Evidently, the postulated event which brought Paleozoic fossils into the ACP occurred in Beacon Hill times (Miocene) was fluvial as it predated the Pleistocene.

Figure 2. Reported Paleozoic fossil sites on the ACP including the eight new sites in this report overlain on surface geology of the ACP and New Jersey Paleozoic limestone formations. Surface geology symbol explanation: Qcm1, Cape May Formation Unit 1. Qs, Swamp and marsh deposits. Qwcp, Weathered Coastal Plain deposits. Tb, Bridgeton Formation. Tp, Pensauken Formation. ArcMap by author (ArcGIS Desktop, online).

Fauna of New Jersey Ordovician-Devonian limestone rocks

Weller has reported the fauna of New Jersey Paleozoic limestone formations with site locations. His taxa are included in **Table 2** (Weller, 1903), notable that brachiopods dominate his reports, but few appear on the ACP. Gallagher (1983) has also reported Paleozoic fauna in these formations, taxa listed in **Table 2**, but, as with Weller, brachiopods

dominate, but few appear on the ACP. Howell and Hale, (1946) also report Paleozoic fossils from the Pensauken Formation at Princeton attributed to the Onondaga Formation, however, their brachiopod suite of eight taxa does not match Weller's suite of 11 brachiopods except for *Atrypa reticularis*. Weller's (1903) taxa are from verified Onondaga Formation sites.

Formation (online)	Description	Anthozoan and poriferid taxa	Systematics
Ordovician			
Kittatinny Limestone	Black chert	No fossils reported (Gallagher, 1983)	

Jacksonburg Limestone	Fossiliferous dark gray limestone	<i>Streptelasma corniculum</i> (Gallagher, 1983)	Rugosa, horn coral
Trenton limestone	Fossiliferous limestone	<i>Hindia parva</i> <i>Receptaculites occidentalis</i> <i>Streptelasma corniculum</i> <i>Nyctopora billingsi</i> (Gallagher, 1983)	Porifera Porifera Rugosa, horn coral Tabulate favositid coral
Silurian			
Bossardville Limestone	Reddish-gray chert	Crinoid columnals, brachiopods, tabulate and rugose corals in Clove Brook Member (Epstein et al., 1947)	
Decker Ferry Formation	Fossiliferous gray chert with rust brown interbeds plus a red limestone member (Weller, 1903) Favositids in thin reddish layers (Gallagher, 1983)	<i>Diphyphyllum integumentum</i> <i>Prismatophyllum inequalis</i> <i>Favosites corrugatus</i> <i>Favosites pyriformis</i> <i>Cladopora rectilineata</i> <i>Halysites catenularia</i> <i>Zaphrentis</i> sp. <i>Stromatopora concentrica</i> (Weller, 1903)	Solitary rugose coral Colonial rugose coral Tabulate favositid coral Tabulate favositid coral Tabulate branching coral Tabulate chain coral Rugosa, horn coral Porifera, stromatoporoid
Rondout Formation	Fossiliferous, no chert reported, medium gray, weathers to dark gray		
Devonian			
Buttermilk Falls Limestone	Fossiliferous, light gray weathers to dark gray nodular black chert	Ostracodes, no anthozoans or poriferids reported (Gallagher, 1983)	
New Scotland Beds	Fossiliferous light to dark gray chert	<i>Hindia fibrosa</i> <i>Streptelasma strictum</i> (Weller, 1903)	Poriferid Rugosa, horn coral
Becraft Formation	Fossiliferous	Crinoidal limestone	
Mahantango Formation	Centerfield Member, calcareous, fossiliferous	<i>Trachypora</i> <i>Syringopora</i> <i>Pleurodictyum</i> (Views of the Mahantango, online) (Natural Atlas, online)	Tabulata Tabulata Tabulata
		<i>Coenites</i> <i>Trachypora</i> <i>Heliophyllum</i> <i>Heterophrentis</i> <i>Zonophyllum</i> <i>Favosites</i> (Gallagher, 1983)	Tabulata Tabulata Rugosa Rugosa Rugosa Tabulata
Onondaga Limestone	Fossiliferous dark chert	<i>Heterophrentiis nitida</i> <i>Favosites turbinatus</i> <i>Favosites goldfussia</i> (Howell and Hale, 1946) <i>Zaphrentis</i> sp (Weller, 1903)	Rugosa, horn coral Tabulate favositid coral Tabulate favositid coral Rugosa, horn coral
Kalkberg Limestone	Fossiliferous black flint nodules. Fossils from New York State occurrence	<i>Streptelasma strictum</i> <i>Favosites helderbergiae</i> <i>Favosites sphaericus</i> <i>Hindia sphaeroidalis</i> (Kalkberg Formation fossils, online)	Rugosa, horn coral Tabulate favositid coral Tabulate favositid coral Poriferid

Coeymans Limestone	Black-gray chert	<i>Zaphrentis roemeri</i> <i>Favosites helderbergiae</i> <i>Cladopora multiserita</i> <i>Favosites</i> sp. (Weller, 1903)	Rugosa, horn coral Tabulate favositid coral Tabulata, branching coral Tabulate favositid coral
Oriskany Formation	Fossiliferous dark gray chert	<i>Emmonosia tuberosus</i> (Gallagher, 1983) <i>Trachypora oriskania</i> <i>Favosites</i> sp. (Weller, 1903)	Tabulata Tabulata, branching coral Tabulate favositid coral
Kanouse Formation (Newfoundland Grit)	yellowish-gray fossiliferous siltstone	<i>Zaphrentis</i> sp. (Weller, 1903)	Rugosa horn coral
Manlius Limestone	Gray chert weathers to buff	No corals (Weller, 1903) Corals reported but not identified (Gallagher, 1983)	

Table 2. New Jersey Ordovician-Devonian Limestone Formations showing their anthozoan and poriferid taxa.

Generalizations deriving from **Table 2.** 1. If a limestone formation is both fossiliferous and contains chert, at least some of the chert will be fossiliferous,

and 2. All listed limestone formations are reported to be fossiliferous except Kittatinny and Coeymans.

Formation	Taxa	Chert	Age
Rondout	None reported in Dolomite members	None reported	Late Silurian to Early Devonian
Poxono	None reported in Dolomite members	None reported	Upper Silurian

Table 3. New Jersey Ordovician-Devonian dolomitic formations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Procedure

- Locate potential parent rocks in New Jersey fossiliferous Paleozoic limestone formations, recording age, color of chert and any other distinctive features.
- Identify the Paleozoic fossils in the fossiliferous New Jersey Paleozoic limestone formations.

- Identify the formations which host exotic Paleozoic fossils on the ACP.
- Identify the exotic Paleozoic fossils found on the ACP.
- Review fluvial and glacial transport models capable of spreading Paleozoic chert over the ACP.
- Compare exotic fossils with counterparts in New Jersey Paleozoic limestone rocks and draw conclusions for parent rocks.
- Report results.

- Most valuable will be index

Site	County	Latitude, dd	Longitude, dd	Altitude, meters	Surface alluvium	Surficial geology
Parvin State Park (Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2000)	Salem	39.508646° N	75.129323° W	23	A	Qwcp (5)
Ramanessin Brook (Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2000) *	Monmouth	40.370861° N	74.175805° W	50	B	Qwcp
Big Brook*	Monmouth	40.320321° N	74.214199° W	21	C	Qwcp
Big Brook tributary (Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2000)	Monmouth	40.318295° N	74.226761° W	26	D	Qwcp
Sunset Beach (Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2000) *	Cape May	38.944327° N	74.970551° W	3	E	Qbs (4)
Stone Bridge (Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2000)	Camden	39.900467° N	75.017301° W	6	F	Qal (6)
Oswego Lake*	Burlington	39.7268° N	74.4924° W	16	G	Qwcp
Lacey Township*	Ocean	39.8597° N	74.207° W	31	H	Qwcp
Deer Park, Bridgeton*	Cumberland	39.426355° N	75.233591° W	2	I	Qwcp
Burlington City*	Burlington	40.07981° N	74.864104° W	2	J	Qs (7)
Mullica Hill*	Gloucester	39.73312° N	75.20737° W	21	K	Qwcp
Princeton (Howell and Hale, 1946)	Mercer	40.356578° N	74.667223° W	47	L	Qal
Asbury Park Beach*	Monmouth	40.22046° N	74.12182° W	3	M	Qcm1(8)
Point Pleasant Beach*	Ocean	40.091365° N	74.036219° W	3	N	Qcm1

Field work

- Screening stream bed float, noting host formation, whether in-situ, coordinates, color, degree of wear and any other notable characteristics.
- Photograph three views of each specimen with scale.

Scope of investigation

- Focus on Class Anthozoa, Subclasses Tabulata and Rugosa, minor Porifera and Brachiopoda.

fossils.

- Search limited to limestone and dolomite formations of Ordovician to Devonian Periods in New Jersey Ridge and Valley and Green Pond Mountain Provinces.

Collecting sites

Exotic Paleozoic fossils have been collected on the ACP from the 14 sites listed in **Table 4**, providing coordinates, altitude, surficial geology and surface alluvium. The eight newly reported sites covered in this report are marked with an asterisk, *, two sites with additional discoveries and six sites previously unreported, total of 14 sites.

Table 4. Paleozoic fossil collection sites on the ACP. Table reference details are included below.

Table 4 reference: Coordinates and altitude from Google Earth.

Site	Surface alluvium (Follerton et al., 2003)
A. Parvin State Park	Channel and flood plain alluvium of Holocene, Pleistocene and Pliocene age
B. Ramanessin Brook	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
C. Big Brook	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
D. Big Brook tributary	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
E. Sunset Beach	Coastal plain and marine deposits of Pleistocene and Pliocene age
F. Stone Bridge	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
G. Oswego Lake	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
H. Lacey Township	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
I. Deer Park, Bridgeton	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
J. Burlington City	Channel and flood plain alluvium of Holocene, Pleistocene and Pliocene age
K. Mullica Hill	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
L. Princeton	Decomposition residue of Quaternary and Tertiary age on other sedimentary rocks
M. Asbury Park Beach	Channel and flood plain alluvium of Holocene, Pleistocene and Pliocene age
N. Point Pleasant Beach	Channel and flood plain alluvium of Holocene, Pleistocene and Pliocene age

Surficial geology mapped across the ACP in **Figure 2** (Newell et al., 2000)

(4). Qbs Beach and Nearshore Marine Sand

(5). Qwcp Weathered Coastal Plain Formations

(6). Qal Alluvium

(7). Qs Swamp And Marsh Deposits

(8). Qcm1 Cape May Formation, Unit 1

RESULTS

Paleozoic fauna

A proportionate faunal profile by class/subclass of the combined eight new collections of Paleozoic fossils on the ACP is provided in **Figure 3**. Tentatively identified

taxa by genus/species are listed in **Table 5**. Many specimens, though, remain unidentified below taxonomic class. The Appendix of this report illustrates type specimens in the Plates, the complete assemblage resides in the Data Repository.

Taxon	Abundance
-------	-----------

Rugosa	
<i>Heliophyllum halli</i>	Common
<i>Heliophyllum canadense</i>	Singular
<i>Neozaphrentis racinensis</i>	Singular
cf. <i>Neozaphrentis wannensis</i>	Singular
<i>Heliophyllum delicatum</i>	Singular
<i>Zaphrentis</i> sp.	Common
cf. <i>Heterophrentis</i> sp.	Singular
cf. <i>Helagonaria anna</i>	Singular
Tabulata	
<i>Favosites favosus</i>	Common
cf. <i>Emmonsia emmonsii</i>	Uncommon
<i>Favosites turbinatus</i>	Uncommon
cf. <i>Pleurodictyum</i> sp.	Uncommon
<i>Favosites tuberosus</i>	Uncommon
cf. <i>Chonostegites</i> sp.	Rare
cf. <i>Syringopora</i> sp.	Uncommon
<i>Trachypora ornata</i>	Uncommon
Favositids	Common
Porifera	
<i>Hindia</i> sp.	Common
<i>Hindia sphaeroidalis</i>	Rare
Stromatoporoid	Uncommon
cf. <i>Archaeocyatha</i> sp.	Singular
cf. <i>Clathrodictyon</i> sp.	Singular
cf. <i>Labechia</i> sp.	Rare
cf. <i>Chaetetes</i> sp.	Uncommon
Brachiopoda	
<i>Leptaena rhomboidalis</i>	Rare
<i>Atrypa</i> sp.	Rare
Spiriferid	Rare
Unidentified	Rare
Crinoidea	
Crinoidea	Uncommon
Arthropoda/Trilobita	
Dalmanitid?	Singular

Table 5. Paleozoic fossil faunal assemblage and relative abundance by class/subclass.

Figure 3. Combined faunal profile of exotic Paleozoic fossils recovered from the eight new sites on the ACP.

The sample size of most collections is too small to reveal significant difference in the fauna composition of the Paleozoic fossils found at the eight sites across the ACP. All eight sites show a similar mix, anthozoans dominant, approximately equally divided between Tabulata and Rugosa, next Porifera. Only six brachiopoda taxa are in the combined collections, all molds except one spiriferid cast. Type specimens are shown in the Appendix Plates:

Plate 1. Porifera

Plate 2. Tabulata

Plate 3. Crinoidea, Rugosa

Plate 4. Brachiopoda, Arthropoda

Size

Solitary rugose corals are free form, all mature, natural size on the order of 50 mm corallum length and dominated by *Zaphrentis*. Favositids are fragmentary averaging 20-30 mm. Although most of

the Paleozoic fossils are worn, their taxa are identifiable which is surprising considering their displacement from parent bedrock exceeds 100 kilometers. The current hypothesis of origin is fluvial in the Neogene Period (Newell et al., 2000), however, according to Sternberg's Law in fluvial transport, clast size decays asymptotically with travel distance as a result of attrition and downgradient sorting (Chatanantavet et al., 2010). Over a travel distance exceeding 100 kilometers, these Paleozoic fossils would have been obliterated if transported fluvially. Additionally, in fluvial transport the degree of roundness increases by the logarithm of the distance traveled so that over a reach of 100 kilometers, only rounds and half rounds (broken rounds) would have survived. The lack of significant wear and a significant number of sharp-edged, pristine specimens suggests ice-rafting transport. Fossils are approximately equally divided between worn, rounded types and sharp-edged pristine types. examples in **Figure 4.**

Figure 4. Wear and weathering effects on favositid corals. L. Minor wear. tabulate, favositid, cf. *Favosites favosus*, tabular view, 40 mm, buff. Ramanessin Brook site. R. Worn, rounded and bleached tabulate, favositid, cf. *Emmonsia emmonsii*, 60 mm wide, white. Mullica Hill site.

Color

Color can aid in tracing exotic Paleozoic fossils to their parent source. Paleozoic chert acquires the hue of its host limestone, however after separation, weathering may alter the hue usually to a lighter shade, rarely darker, depending upon the length of time exposed subaerially or submerged and so masks its origin. The largest proportion of Paleozoic fossils on the ACP included in this report are buff in color (Figure 5) attributed to weathering as the Paleozoic limestone formations and their associated chert in northern New Jersey are dominantly gray and black in color Table 2. White chert may be the result of

such weathering. In New Jersey Paleozoic limestone, red chert is only found in one member of the Decker Ferry Formation and reddish gray chert in the Bossardville Limestone Formation (Table 2). Red hued specimens are the second largest category of exotic Paleozoic fossils and are dominant at the Big Brook and Ramanessin Brook sites. On beach and near shore Holocene sites, Lacey Township, Asbury Park Beach, Pt. Pleasant Beach and Sunset Beach, 50% of specimens are black, an indication that sea water immersion may inhibit weathering.

Figure 5. Fossiliferous chert on the ACP, color profile.

Form

Most of the Paleozoic fossils are free form, out of matrix, but about 10% are embedded in nodular

chert, examples in Figure 6. This characteristic may be related to limestone formations with chert in

layers rather than nodules although no searches by type of chert were conducted in this investigation.

Figure 6. Comparison of in-matrix and free form Paleozoic fossils. L. Brachiopod *Leptaena rhomboidalis* internal mold in nodular chert matrix, Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH101. R. Free form rugose solitary coral *Heliophyllum canadense*, Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH107.

Encrustations

Some of the calices of the solitary rugose corals, cf. *Heliophyllum*, are filled with chaetetid sponge mats, **Figure 7, R**. Such mats are formed on dead corals in an intertidal zone making the sponge encrustations

younger than their host. Some of the favositid tabulate corals are encrusted with thin algal-microbial mats (stromatoporoids) **Figure 7, L**.

Figure 7. Alien encrustations on Paleozoic fossils. L. Stromatoporoid on favositid coral, cf. *Favosites favosus*, tabular view, Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection. R. Chaetetid sponge on solitary rugose coral, cf. *Heliophyllum* sp., calicular view, filling the calix and covering most of the septa. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 105.

Photographs, systematics and descriptions of representative type specimens are included in the Plates located in the Appendix of this report. Systematics, descriptions and photographs of all specimens reside in the Data Repository.

DISCUSSION

- Conventional geology postulates that silicified fossils were captured from colluvium derived from biogenic Paleozoic limestone rocks of the New Jersey Ridge and Valley and

the Green Pond Mountain Outlier Provinces or north in New York State and deposited on the Miocene Beacon Hill Gravel Formation which once overspread much of the Outer Coastal Plain of New Jersey. Evidently, this event, or events, was fluvial as it occurred before the Pleistocene. Pleistocene outwash and erosion has since scattered the Beacon Hill Paleozoic chert fossils at least over the Outer Coastal Plain and possibly over the entire ACP. A second stream may have

descended down along the Delaware River along the Amboy-Salem trench on the Inner Coastal Plain.

- Inland site collectors affirm that, to the best of their knowledge, their sites were free of extraneous material confirming that their specimens were native to surficial geology formations and associated alluvium as shown in this report. Beach sites may have been replenished, but, as material is normally excavated from just offshore, the inferences from these sites as expressed in this report, remain valid.
- This investigation did not achieve its primary aim of locating the parent Paleozoic rocks for the fossils found on the ACP. This may be because the faunal assemblage of potential parent Paleozoic rocks is incomplete or may be due to nomenclature differences over time.
- The presence of identifiable Paleozoic fossils at such great distances from their parent rocks, many little worn and sharp-edged, does not favor extended fluvial transport.
- Finding exotic Paleozoic fossils at 14 diverse locations suggests that they are ubiquitous across the ACP. Neither is the phenomenon limited to the ACP as exotic Paleozoic fossils have also been recovered from midwestern and southern sites far from their source rocks.
- An intention of this investigation is to encourage other collectors to recover and report exotic fossils along with their primary paleontological interest.

CONCLUSION

Most of the 131 Exotic Paleozoic fossils found at eight new sites on the ACP have been identified to their taxonomic order, many speciated. Fossil suites of potential parent Paleozoic chert-bearing bedrock limestone in New Jersey were also examined, however, below taxonomic class/subclass there was little correlation between the two groups. Specimens from the

ACP interior sites, Big Brook and Ramanessin Brook are dominantly red in color as are some specimens from other sites suggesting their parent is the Decker Ferry, Silurian limestone, the only formation in the Paleozoic rocks of New Jersey which has a red member. No fossils are confirmed in-situ in ACP formations but have been recovered from stream bed float, alluvium and Holocene beach gravels. The low degree of wear and weathering on fossils at least 100 kilometers distant from any potential parent source challenges the conventional notion of fluvial transport.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to Shane Hajzer, Carl Mehling and Fiona Brady for their contributions of specimens included in this investigation.

DATA REPOSITORY

Systematics, photographs and descriptions of all collections of Paleozoic fossils included in this report are available online at: DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10504.70405

PUBLISHED REFERENCES

- Barnett, S., 1974, Geology of the Paleozoic Rocks of the Green Pond Outlier, Department of Earth Sciences, State University of New York, Plattsburgh, NY. 14 pp.
- Chatanantavet, P., Lajeunesse, E., Parker, G., Malverti, G. and Meunier, P., 2010, Physically based model of downstream fining in bedrock streams with lateral input. *Water Resour.* 46, W02518. doi:10.1029/2008WR007208
- Dalton, R., Monteverde, D., Sugarman P. and Volkert, R., 2014, Bedrock Geologic Map of New Jersey; New Jersey Geological and Water Survey, Trenton, NJ. Map.
- Epstein, A., Epstein, J., Spink, W. and Jennings, D., 1947, Upper Silurian and Lower Devonian Stratigraphy of Northeastern Pennsylvania,

- New Jersey, and Southeasternmost New York. Geological Survey Bulletin 1243. U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA.
- Fariakas, G., Nemickas, B. and Gill, H., 1978, Geology and Ground-Water Resources of Camden County, New Jersey. U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA. 146 pages.
- Fullerton, D., Bush, C. and Pennell, J., 2003, Map of Surficial Deposits and Materials in the Eastern and Central United States (East of 102° West Longitude). U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA. Map.
- Gallagher, W., 1981, Paleontology and Ecology along the New Jersey Shore, Delaware Valley Paleontological Society Newsletter, Vol. 3, No. 9.
- Gallagher, W., 1983, Paleoecology of the Delaware Valley Region, Part I: Cambrian to Jurassic. *The Mosasaur*, Vol I., pp 23-42.
- Howell, B. and Hale, H., 1946, Fossiliferous pebbles in "Pennsauken Gravel" at Princeton, New Jersey. *J. Geol.* 54(6). pp. 386-390.
- Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A., 2020, Paleozoic Fossils of the New Jersey Atlantic Coastal Plain. *The Mosasaur*, Vol XI., pp 59-91.
- Landmeyer J., Tourneur F., Denayer J. and Zapalski M., 2019, Fossil tabulate corals reveal outcrops of Paleozoic sandstones in the Atlantic Coastal Plain Province, Southeastern USA. *PLoS ONE* 14(10): e0224248. 13 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224248>
- Morris, R., 2010, Fossiliferous cherts of the Midwest: Their origin, composition and prehistoric use. *Ohio Archeologist*, 60(1). pp. 25-31.3.
- Newell, W., Powars, D., Owens, J., Stanford, S. and Stone, B., 2000, Surficial Geologic Map of Central and Southern New Jersey, MAP I-2540-D and Text to accompany MAP I-2540-D. U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA.
- Pickett, T. and Windish, D., 1992, Delaware: its rocks, minerals, and fossils. Special Publication No. 19. Delaware Geological Survey. Newark, DE. 19 pages.
- Salisbury, R. and Knapp, G., 1917, The Quaternary Formations of Southern New Jersey. Vol. VIII of the Final Report Series of the State Geologist, New Jersey Department of Conservation and Development, Trenton, NJ. 233 pages.
- Stanford, S., 2020, Surface Geology of the Lakehurst Quadrangle, Open File OFM Map 127. New Jersey Geological and Water Survey, Trenton, NJ. Map.
- Weller, S., 1903, Report on the paleontology of New Jersey, Volume III. The Paleozoic faunas. New Jersey Geological Survey. Trenton, NJ. 520 pages.

ONLINE REFERENCES

- ArcGIS Desktop. Release 10, 2011, Environmental Systems Research Institute, Redlands, CA. Available online: <https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-desktop/overview>. (Accessed 20 January 2022).
- Becraft. National Geologic Map Database. Available online: https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/BecraftRefs_345.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Bossardville Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online: https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/BossardvilleRefs_568.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Buttermilk Falls Limestone/Onondaga Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available

- online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NJDb%3B7> (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Chert, What is Chert? How does it form? What is it used for? Available online:
<https://geology.com/rocks/chert.shtml> (accessed 14 August 2021).
- Coeymans Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NJDkc%3B7> (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Decker Ferry Formation. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/WallpackCenterRefs_4279.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- The Fossil Forum, Available online:
<http://www.thefossilforum.com/> (accessed 5 August 2021). FossilSites.com, US And Canadian Fossil Sites -- Data for New Jersey. Available online:
<http://www.fossilspot.com/STATES/NJ.HTM> (accessed 30 August 2021).
- Jacksonburg Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/JacksonburgRefs_2212.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Kalkberg Formation, Views of the Mahantango. Available online:
<http://viewsofthemahantango.blogspot.com/p/kalkberg-formation-fossils.html> (accessed 6 January 2022).
- Kalkberg Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/KalkbergRefs_2272.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Kanouse Formation. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NJDkcc%3B6> (accessed 27 January 2022).
- Kittatinny Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/KittatinnyRefs_2337.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Mahantango. Available online:
<https://www.primidi.com/mahantango> (accessed 25 January 2022).
- Manlius Limestone. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NJDkc%3B7> (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Natural Atlas. Available online:
<https://naturalatlas.com/geologic-formations/mahantango-formation-2773838> (accessed 28 January 2022).
- New Scotland Beds. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/NewScotlandRefs_2987.html (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Onondaga. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NYDou%3B2> (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Oriskany Formation. National Geologic Map Database. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NYDo%3B2> (accessed 4 August 2021).
- Poxono Island Formation. Available online:
<https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/state/sgmc-unit.php?unit=NJSp%3B7> (accessed 27 August 2021).

Rondout. National Geologic Map Database.
Available online:
https://ngmdb.usgs.gov/Geolex/UnitRefs/RondoutRefs_3624.html (accessed 27 August 2021).

Silicification, Paleontological Paper V-20.
Available online:
<http://peabody.yale.edu/sites/default/files/documents/invertebrate-paleontology/ButtsPSP20FinalOPEN.pdf>
(accessed 14 August 2021).

Silicified fossil coral Middle Paleozoic; gravel bar clast, Chatham, Ohio, USA. St. John. J.
Available online:
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/jsjgeology/26370187737/in/photostream/> (accessed 4 August 2021).

APPENDIX

Systematics and descriptions of representative specimens. Consult the Data Repository for a complete listing of specimens and photographs with references used for identification.

Plate 1 key: Porifera

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	9
10	11	12
13	14	15

1. cf. *Hindia* sp., Internal view, 28 mm, red. Ordovician to Permian. Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection.
2. External view of 1.
3. cf. *Hindia* sp., external view, 22 mm, white. Oswego Lake, Frank Hajzer collection.
4. Stromatoporoid, cf. *Clathrodictyon* sp., 45 mm, red. Devonian Columbus Formation of Ontario, Canada. Frank Hajzer collection.
5. Stromatoporoid, mamelon view, 20 mm, buff. Oswego Lake, Frank Hajzer collection.
6. Stromatoporoid encrustation on favositid tabulate coral, cf. *Favosites favosus*, 15 mm, buff. Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection.
7. Archaeocyathid, cf. *Archaeocyatha* sp., 12 mm, buff. Cambrian. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 170.
8. Archaeocyathid, cf. *Archaeocyatha* sp., 35 mm overall, brown, at least 8 individuals showing, 4 mm. Cambrian. Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection.
9. Empty.
10. cf. *Solenopora compacta*, 25 mm, black. Oswego Lake. Frank Hajzer collection.
11. Reverse side view of 10.
12. Chaetetid sponge encrustation on solitary rugose coral, cf. *Heliophyllum* sp., calicular view, 33 mm, white. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 105.
13. Chaetetid sponge. 20 mm, red, Oswego Lake, Frank Hajzer collection.
14. Chaetetid sponge, circular structure on crinoidal limestone. 25 mm, black, Sunset Beach, Frank Hajzer collection.
15. Stromatoporoid, cf. *Labechia* sp. 45 mm long, buff. Silurian, Earlington, Ontario. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 112.

PLATE 1

Plate 2 key: Tabulata

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	9

1. Favositid, cf. *Favosites* sp., tabular view, 40 mm, buff. Ramanessin Brook. Frank Hajzer collection.
2. Favositid, cf. *Favosites* sp., calicular view, 20 mm, red. Oswego Lake. Frank Hajzer collection.
3. Favositid, cf. *Favosites turbinatus*, 43 mm, white. Mullica Hill. Les Spears collection, MH 114.
4. cf. *Pleurodictyum convexum*, longitudinal view, 44 mm, white, Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 128.
5. cf. *Chonostegites* sp., 30 mm, white, conical shape, lattice pattern on sides, corallites 0.5 to 1 mm, Niagara County, New York. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 162.
6. cf. *Thamnoptychia* (Trachypora) *Trachypora* sp., Devonian to Pennsylvanian. Hamilton Formation, NY, cf. *Trachypora ornata*. Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection.
7. Favositid. 35 mm, buff, agatized coral geode. Lacey Township. Frank Hajzer collection.
8. Side view of 7. Note diagnostic tabulae.
9. cf. *Cladopora* sp. Specimen 50 mm, white. Devonian Onondaga Limestone of Williamsville, NY

PLATE 2

Plate 3 key: Crinoidea, Rugosa

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	9
10	11	12
13	14	15

1. Crinoidea, 10 mm, white. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 177.
2. Crinoidea, 30 mm, red. Burlington, Frank Hajzer collection.
3. Crinoidea, cf. *Apiocrinus* sp., Crinoidal limestone, 20 cm, black, oxidized to red on surface, Delaware River shore gravel, Burlington City, Frank Hajzer collection.
4. Crinoidal limestone close up of 3. red, 8 mm diameter columnal segments. Sunset Beach, Frank Hajzer collection.
5. Crinoidal limestone, black, Sunset Beach, Frank Hajzer collection.
6. Rugosa, cf. *Heliophyllum* sp. 33 mm long, white, large solitary horn coral, cylindrical, calice 20 mm with fossula, septa and columella, found in New York and Ontario, Lower and Middle Devonian, Mullica Hill. Les Spears collection, MH 109.
7. Rugosa, cf. *Heliophyllum halli*. 16 mm, buff. calicular view. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 103.
8. Rugosa, cf. *Heliophyllum canadense*, 31mm long, horn coral, calice 23 mm wide, buff. Devonian Onondaga limestone of Mendon, Ontario, Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection MH 107.
9. Rugosa, cf. *Zaphrentis* sp. 18 mm, buff. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 149.
10. Rugosa, cf. *Heterophrentis* sp., internal mold, Devonian, NY, Oswego Lake, Frank Hajzer collection.
11. Rugosa. cf. *Helagonaria anna*, colonial rugose coral, 30 mm, buff, Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 108.
12. Rugosa, group of solitary individuals (10), Chaetetid sponge inhabiting the calices, 40 mm overall, brown, calice diameter about 4 mm.
13. Rugosa, solitary, agatized coral geode. 27 mm, black, Lacey Township, Frank Hajzer collection.
14. Bottom view of 12.
15. Side view of 12.

PLATE 3

Plate 4 key: Brachiopoda, Arthropoda

1	2	3
4	5	6
7		

1. Spiriferid, External mold, 5 mm on 25 mm white poriferid, cf. *Hindia* sp. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH 172.
2. cf. *Leptaena rhomboidalis*, internal mold. 30 mm, buff, Ordovician (Llanvirn) – Devonian (Pragian? Emsian). Devonian of New York and Pennsylvania. Mullica Hill, Les Spears collection, MH101.
3. Spiriferid, internal cast. red. Ramanessin Brook, Carl Mehling collection.
4. Brachiopoda, internal mold, 37 mm, buff. Bridgeton, Shane Hajzer collection.
5. cf. *Atrypa* sp. on fenestrate bryozoan, 8 mm, white, Lacey Township, Frank Hajzer collection.
6. Brachiopoda, internal molds, 2 mm. buff, Big Brook, Frank Hajzer collection.
7. Trilobite, cf. dalmanitid, Silurian or Early Devonian. 30 mm. Carl Mehling collection.

PLATE 4

